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Spin-wave microscale RF delay lines for mid- and high-frequency 5G band ^{EP}

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ABSTRACT

Delay lines (DL) are crucial components in communication systems, providing the required time delays for signal timing, synchronization, and processing. DLs providing nanosecond-scale delays are conventionally based on acoustic waves; however, they cannot operate conveniently in a high-frequency range (EU 5G high-band 24.25–27.5 GHz) required by a modern generation of 5G communication technologies to speed up data transfer. The proposed solution is to use DL based on spin-wave (SW) transmission, as SW devices allow for operation at high-frequency ranges and can be scaled down to a few μm^2 . In this study, we investigate SW-based DL at the microscale at the frequency ranges of 4, 9, and 25 GHz. The DL is based on SW transmission between a pair of 250 nm wide microwave coplanar waveguide transducers, each with a footprint of $2.25 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$, and fabricated with varying mutual distances on a 97 nm thin yttrium iron garnet film. DLs are tested for in-plane SW modes (Damon–Eshbach and backward volume), and depending on the parameters, the extracted delay times are in the range of 6–165 ns. Furthermore, the insertion losses are extracted and compared to other DL concepts. Time-gating analysis of the measured transmission is performed, providing a detailed discussion of individual signal contributions to the measured spectra. Additionally, analytical theory is employed to compare the experimental delay times with analytical calculations and to predict how to adjust the device parameters to obtain variable time delays.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Communication systems urgently need to speed up data transfer due to the increasing number of active user devices every year.¹ Therefore, the aim of modern 5G technology systems is to move from standard frequency ranges (e.g., EU 5G low-band 694–790 MHz and mid-band 3.4–3.8 GHz) to high-frequency ranges (e.g., EU 5G

high-band 24.25–27.5 GHz). However, moving to higher frequency ranges is challenging for many radio frequency (RF) devices, such as filters, limiters, and delay lines that are conventionally used at lower frequency ranges.²

Delay lines (DLs) are two-port devices that delay signal transmission by a fixed amount of time to synchronize signals. This is crucial for error reduction in signal processing, timing, and phase

shifting, especially in multi-band and multi-antenna systems used in modern 5G communication systems.²

In telecommunication systems, either photonic or acoustic DLs are conventionally used for on-chip signal processing applications. DLs based on photonic integrated circuits (PICs)^{3–7} leverage the propagation of light through optical waveguides and offer several advantages, including broadband operation, performance up to THz frequency range, and small insertion losses. However, since on-chip PIC-based DLs provide delay times in the ps range, it remains challenging to simultaneously achieve tunability, longer delay times (at the ns range), and a small device footprint.^{3,4}

The synchronization requirements and delay compensations needed for 5G networks are from picoseconds to a few hundred nanoseconds.^{8,9}

Therefore, searching for a technology providing longer delay times is of interest. One of the suitable candidates are acoustic DLs based either on surface acoustic waves (SAWs)^{10–18} or on bulk acoustic waves (BAWs).^{19–22} SAW-based DLs can provide delay times in the range of a few ns up to several hundred ns. However, they can operate conveniently only in the low GHz range (approx. up to 3 GHz¹¹) because of the significantly increasing damping of acoustic waves with increasing frequency, resulting in high insertion losses.¹² Additionally, operating SAW DLs at higher frequencies requires proportionally smaller interdigitated transducers (IDTs), which poses significant challenges for conventional optical lithography techniques used for their fabrication.¹³ Compared to SAW-based DLs, BAW-based DLs can provide significantly longer delay times in the range of a few hundred ns up to several hundred ms, and they can also operate at slightly higher frequency ranges (up to approximately 6 GHz).²³ However, BAW-based DLs suffer from complicated fabrication due to the high requirements for BAW isolation from the substrate and increasing damping with increasing frequency.¹³

Therefore, it is of interest for the next generation of communication technology to search for a DL capable of operating in the high frequency range (around 25 GHz) and simultaneously providing longer delay times (in the ns range). One possible solution can be DLs based on spin-wave (SW) transmission, as they allow effective operation at high-frequency ranges with provided delay times in the ns range. Moreover, SW-based DLs are frequency flexible (the same device can operate at any frequency range defined by the external magnetic field), are easy to fabricate, and allow for device miniaturization.^{2,24} Additionally, SW-based devices provide multifunctionality, meaning that a single SW device can simultaneously work as a delay line, filter, and power limiter.²⁴ Furthermore, the delay time can be precisely tuned by the choice of the magnetic material (sample thickness, saturation magnetization), antenna design (mutual distance between the antennas), and applied magnetic field, determining the frequency range and SW mode.^{25–29} However, in the past, SW-based DLs have been investigated mostly at the macroscale,^{30–36} in the centimeter and millimeter ranges, and in the low-frequency ranges (up to 5 GHz). Only recently, in 2023, Li *et al.*³⁷ demonstrated nanoscale spin-wave delay lines based on 100 nm thin YIG films, employing coplanar-waveguide (CPW) antennas with a width of 200 nm and a length of 30 μm . These devices, characterized in the Damon–Eshbach (DE) mode up to 14 GHz, exhibited delay times of 23, 47, and 96 ns at 10 GHz for

propagation distances of 5 μm , 10 μm , and 20 μm , respectively. Nevertheless, the reported devices exhibit high insertion losses exceeding 50 dB, were not characterized in the desired high-frequency range up to 25 GHz, and were tested exclusively for the Damon–Eshbach mode. However, the backward volume mode is particularly relevant for 5G high-band applications, as it exhibits significantly lower insertion losses at 25 GHz compared to the Damon–Eshbach mode.²⁴

In this study, we investigate nanoscale DLs based on the spin-wave transmission between a pair of 250 nm wide microwave CPW transducers, each with a footprint of $2.25 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$, of different mutual center-to-center spacings, which are fabricated on the 97 nm thin yttrium iron garnet (YIG) film. The DLs are tested in a broad frequency range of 4, 9, and 25 GHz for both in-plane SW modes—Damon–Eshbach (DE, applied field is perpendicular to the SW propagation) and backward volume (BV, applied field is parallel to SW propagation). To extract the delay time, a time-gating analysis of the measured SW transmission is performed, providing a detailed discussion of the various signal contributions, including electromagnetic leakage, and explaining the oscillations in the measured SW spectra. The extracted delay times are compared with analytical calculations, and the possibility of obtaining variable delay times by tuning the device parameters (such as sample thickness, or using different SW modes) is discussed. Furthermore, the quantitative comparison of the extracted insertion losses is presented and compared to other DL devices. To explain the different delay times and insertion losses observed for the two spin-wave modes, calculated dispersion relations, group velocities, lifetimes, and decay lengths are provided for both modes.

II. NANOSCALE SW-BASED DELAY LINES

The DL devices consist of CPW transducers and a magnetic film. As a magnetic medium, the 97 nm thin liquid phase epitaxy (LPE) grown YIG film on (111) gallium gadolinium garnet (GGG) is used because of favorable damping characteristics,³⁸ resulting in long propagation distances of spin waves. On top of the YIG layer, the microwave transducers are fabricated using PMMA resist and e-beam lithography, followed by metal evaporation (10 nm Ti, 320 nm Cu, 20 nm Au) and lift-off. The fabricated transducers consist of three fingers, each 250 nm wide with 750 nm spacing, and a length of 100 μm . The center-to-center distance between the transducers is 3, 7.5, and 52.5 μm , and their total thickness is 350 nm; see Fig. 1.

The microwave transducers are connected via picoprobes and coaxial cables to the vector network analyzer (VNA), which generates and detects microwave signals (electromagnetic waves, EM). For characterization of DLs, propagating spin-wave spectroscopy (PSWS)^{24,39,40} is used. The principle is the following: the DL device is located in the external magnetic field, and the microwave current generated by the VNA is sent to the input transducer. The microwave current creates an alternating magnetic field around the transducer, which interacts with the magnetic moments in the magnetic layer beneath. If the frequency of the microwave current matches the SW dispersion relation (determined by the external magnetic field and material parameters, see Appendix A), spin waves are generated, and they propagate in the magnetic film. When they

FIG. 1. SEM images of SW-based DLs consisting of microwave transducers on the YIG film. The lengths of the transducers are $100\ \mu\text{m}$, and both signal (S) and ground (G) conductors are $250\ \text{nm}$ wide and $750\ \text{nm}$ apart from each other. The center-to-center distance D between the transducers is (a) $D = 3\ \mu\text{m}$, (b) $D = 7.5\ \mu\text{m}$, and (c) $D = 52.5\ \mu\text{m}$. Spin-wave propagation between the input and output transducers and the signal conversion between electromagnetic (EM) and spin-wave (SW) signals are indicated in (c).

reach the output transducer, the alternating magnetic field (created by magnetic moment precession) induces a voltage in the output transducer, which is detected by the VNA. The transmitted SW signal can be represented by the scattering parameter S_{21} , which is the ratio of the detected and generated signals.

The time delay T_d is determined by the SW group velocity v_g and the distance D between the transducers,

$$T_d = \frac{D}{v_g}. \quad (1)$$

The SW group velocity is a derivative of the SW dispersion relation

$$v_g = \frac{2\pi\partial f}{\partial k}, \quad (2)$$

which is calculated from the analytical model of Kalinikos and Slavin,⁴¹ see Appendix A.

III. MEASUREMENTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

We characterize the fabricated DLs described in the previous section using the time-gating analysis.^{37,42–46} SW transmission is measured using VNA in the frequency domain,^{24,39,40,42,47,48} and then the inverse Fourier transform (IFT) is applied to convert the measured data into the time domain. This emulates propagation of a very short pulse (with the duration being the inverse frequency

band accounted for in the calculations—see Appendix B) and allows for distinguishing all the possible contributions to the transmission. The analysis of a finite-length pulse propagation is discussed later. In the time domain, we identify and extract the signal of interest, a peak whose amplitude corresponds to a specific delay time T_d . To gain deeper insight into the time-domain data, the Fourier transform (FT) of the signal of interest (extracted peak with annulled surroundings) is applied to convert this signal back to the frequency domain for comparison with the original data. This time-gating analysis enables the identification of the individual signal contributions and their origin in the measured transmission, allowing for further optimization of SW devices by eliminating unwanted signal components. Please note that the time-gating analysis is applicable only to time-invariant linear systems.

Moreover, in many cases, the SW signal in the measured transmission is very weak, particularly in a few-nanometer-thick structured YIG films. The standard procedure to eliminate parasitic signals (e.g., electromagnetic leakage) typically involves subtracting the reference transmission (measured at different magnetic fields) from the transmission of interest, which is both time-consuming and prone to inaccuracies. Compared to this standard method of background subtraction, time-gating is highly efficient in finding the signal of interest in the measured transmission spectrum in the frequency domain.

The time-gating analysis of all signal contributions in the transmission spectra measured using transducers with a center-to-center distance of $7.5\ \mu\text{m}$, at $71\ \text{mT}$ in DE mode is shown in Fig. 2. The VNA parameters used are input power $-30\ \text{dBm}$, bandwidth $1\ \text{kHz}$, frequency step $200\ \text{kHz}$, and no averaging. The measured SW transmission in the frequency domain (original raw data) at $3\text{--}5\ \text{GHz}$ is plotted in gray in the bottom row in Fig. 2(a). The IFT of the measured (raw) data in the time domain is also plotted in gray in the middle row in Fig. 2(a). The signal of interest in the time domain is highlighted in color for each column, and its FT is plotted in the same color in the frequency domain. In the following text, the individual signal contributions, depicted in the top row in Fig. 2(a), are described.

- *The first column I.* The fastest signal that is detected by the second VNA port is the electromagnetic leakage, i.e., the cross-talk between the transducers.⁴⁹ The electromagnetic leakage creates the background in the frequency domain, and it is of interest to reduce it as much as possible to have the best signal-to-noise ratio for the SW signal.
- *The second column II.* After the electromagnetic leakage, the main SW signal takes place. Compared to electromagnetic leakage, the SW signal is slower as it propagates at a speed of the SW group velocity (in this case $v_g = 598\ \text{m/s}$) from the input to the output transducer. This propagation defines the delay time T_d , which is extracted from the measured data as $T_d = 13.6 \pm 3.2\ \text{ns}$. The theoretical delay time T_d^* , determined by the distance between the transducers and the SW group velocity [see Eq. (1)], is $T_d^* = 12.5\ \text{ns}$ and agrees well with the experimental one. The SW signal maximum ($-27\ \text{dB}$) is $29\ \text{dB}$ larger than the median value of the electromagnetic leakage ($-56\ \text{dB}$) extracted at the frequency range of the SW signal ($3.8\text{--}4.3\ \text{GHz}$).

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FIG. 2. (a) In the top row: Different signal contributions—the electromagnetic leakage (the curved arrow in I.), the SW signal with small wavenumbers that undergo reflections from the transducers (straight arrows in II., III., IV., and V.), and the SW signal with large wavenumbers (double-arrow in III.). In gray, the bottom row: Measured SW transmission using the transducers with the distance of $7.5\ \mu\text{m}$ in DE mode. In gray, the middle row: The IFT of the measured transmission to the time domain. In color: The signal of interest in the time domain is highlighted in color, and its FT with the annulled background back to the frequency domain is highlighted in the same color. In columns: The individual signal contributions are highlighted and compared to the original data in each column. (b) The interference of two signals causes the oscillations in the measured SW transmission (in gray). The signal contributions in the time domain are highlighted in light green for the main SW peak and in dark green for the side SW peak. (c) The SW transmission (in gray) occurs at the frequency range that matches the intersection of the SW dispersion relation (in black) and the transducer excitation efficiency (in blue). The arrows symbolizing the individual signal contributions in (a) are assigned to the first and second peaks in the excitation spectra. (d) The details of the interference of two SW signals with different wavenumbers in the time domain in III. The distance between two maxima in the time domain (2 ns) corresponds to the distance in frequency between the main and the side SW signal, as highlighted in dark cyan in (c).

- *The third column III.* The next signal contribution appears as an interference of two signals. We see a pronounced beating in the time domain with a period $\Delta T \approx 2$ ns, as evidenced in the zoomed-in signal profile in Fig. 2(d). The reconstructed spectrum of this signal of interest contains two peaks, one at the same frequency position as the main SW peak discussed just above (around 4 GHz) and the second at about 4.5 GHz. Frequency separation between the peaks $\Delta f \approx 0.5$ GHz gives the period of beating in the time domain $\Delta T = 1/\Delta f$. Both of these peaks originate from the SW signal. The frequencies (f) and wavenumbers (k) of the generated spin waves in the measured transmission [gray curve in Fig. 2(c)] are determined by the intersection of the SW dispersion relation [black curve in

Fig. 2(c)] and transducer excitation spectra J_{exc} [blue curve in Fig. 2(c)]; see Appendix A for more details. The main SW signal contribution in the measured data is from the first peak in the excitation spectra at $k = 3.1$ rad/ μm (wavelength $\lambda = 2.026\ \mu\text{m}$), and the side contribution is from the second peak $k_s = 9.3$ rad/ μm ($\lambda_s = 0.675\ \mu\text{m}$). The SW group velocities differ within the main peak ($v_g = 598$ m/s) and side peak ($v_{g,s} = 316$ m/s). Theoretical delay for shorter SW (secondary peak) is $T_{d,s}^* = D/v_{g,s} = 23.8$ ns, close to the measured one $T_d = 29.5 \pm 4.5$ ns. Thus, the signal from the second peak in the excitation spectra is the SW signal at a smaller wavelength that propagates as a common one-way from the excitation toward the detection transducer. The nature of the signal at the

main excitation peak is more nontrivial. To match theoretical delay time with the experimental one, we need to assume that the signal propagates the doubled distance, i.e., $T_d^* = 2D/v_g = 25.0$ ns. Thus, the signal from the first peak of the excitation spectra originates from the SWs that travel from the excitation transducer toward the detection transducer and back. We assume that this signal contribution is present in the measured transmission due to the interference of this reflected SW signal with the electromagnetic leakage signal that is being generated at the emitting transducer and detected at the output, as we are operating at the continuous-wave (CW) mode. Because the two aforementioned delay times are similar, the interference occurs, see Fig. 2(d). Both discussed contributions are weak compared to the main SW peak (column II)—24.5 dB smaller for the second excitation peak contribution and 28.2 dB smaller for the double reflected signal.

- *The fourth and the fifth columns IV. and V.* In the fourth and fifth columns, the SW signals with two and three reflections from the transducers are highlighted. Its theoretical delay times $T_d^* = 3D/v_g = 37.5$ ns and $T_d^* = 4D/v_g = 50.0$ ns agree reasonably with the experimental one $T_d = 41.0 \pm 5.2$ ns and $T_d = 53.0 \pm 3.1$ ns. The differences between the contributions from the signals with two reflections (−48 dB) and three reflections (−61 dB) from the transducers are 21 and 24 dB compared to the main SW signal maximum (−27 dB). We assume that, also in this case, the SW signal with three reflections is present in the measured transmission due to the interference with the electromagnetic leakage when reaching the emitting transducer.

Based on this analysis, the main SW signal exceeds the electromagnetic leakage by 29 dB, the side peak from the second excitation maxima by 24.5 dB, and the contribution from two reflections on the transducers by 21 dB. Therefore, despite the presence of these parasitic signals, the DL performance remains good, with a margin exceeding 20 dB.

Moreover, this time-gating analysis is particularly useful for understanding the original data measured in the frequency domain (in gray). Both the main and the side SW signals exhibit some oscillations; see Fig. 2(b). These oscillations are caused by the interference of two signals. To explain their origin, an IFT must be performed simultaneously for two signals of interest with an annulled background.

The oscillations observed in the main SW peak arise when the IFT is calculated from the superposition of the SW signal propagating once between the transducers and the signal undergoing three round trips between them. These contributions in the time domain are highlighted in light green in Fig. 2(b). For certain applications, such as SW-based filters, it is essential to minimize these oscillations to achieve a well-defined peak shape, ideally as close as possible to a rectangular profile. The oscillations originate from SW reflections at the interface between the metal transducers and the YIG film, and can be suppressed by introducing an insulating layer between the transducers and the film. However, a trade-off arises: while a thicker insulating layer reduces the reflections more effectively, it also decreases the efficiency of SW excitation and detection due to the increased separation from the YIG film. Alternatively, parasitic reflections can be mitigated by fully metallizing the YIG film in DE mode^{35,50} and employing the “inverse approach,” in

which the entire surface is covered by metals except for the antenna gaps. Another potential strategy is the use of antennas with a gradual increase in thickness, enabling the SWs to adapt progressively and thereby reducing reflections through a smoother transition in wavenumber.

The oscillations in the side peak are caused by the interference between the SW signal originating from the second peak in the excitation spectrum and the electromagnetic leakage, as highlighted in dark green in Fig. 2(b). While the electromagnetic leakage interferes with all signal components, pronounced oscillations appear only when the SW signal is comparable to or smaller in magnitude than the electromagnetic leakage. Therefore, for SW devices, it is crucial to minimize electromagnetic leakage as much as possible, thus achieving a better signal-to-noise ratio and avoiding unwanted oscillations in the signal of interest. Electromagnetic leakage can be reduced by optimizing the transducer design, particularly the transducer pads used for contacting the picoprobes.

A real device is operating with finite-length pulses⁵¹ (units up to tens of nanoseconds) that have relatively narrow frequency spectra rather than a wide uniform spectrum in the whole measurement band (which mimics in our case a pulse of just 0.5 ns length, as we take 2 GHz band into consideration). To analyze transmission of such pulses, we consider a normalized 10 ns long Gaussian pulse [Fig. 3(a)] and 5 ns long square pulse [Fig. 3(e)] at the carrier frequency of 4.1 GHz. The calculations are done in a standard way—the pulse frequency spectra [blue curves in Figs. 3(b) and 3(f)] are multiplied by the amplitude-frequency characteristics of the delay line, which is nothing else than the measured frequency-dependent SW transmission in continuous mode [gray curves in Figs. 3(b) and 3(f)]. The resulting spectra of the transmitted signals [dark blue curves in Figs. 3(c) and 3(g)] are then converted back to the time domain using IFT, where they are compared with the original data; see Figs. 3(d) and 3(h).

From this comparison, it is visible that the second peak (at about 30 ns delay) is suppressed for both excitation pulses (Gaussian and square), because the second excitation maximum in the antenna spectrum lies outside the signal bandwidth and therefore does not contribute to the transmission. Also, the oscillations of the transmitted signal are suppressed for the same reason. The suppression of the second peak is more pronounced when using the Gaussian pulse, as there are no side products in the frequency domain compared to the square pulse; see blue curves in Figs. 3(b) and 3(f). Other peaks, with a delay of about 41 and 53 ns, are still there, meaning that these peaks originate from the SW signal that undergoes multiple reflections. At the same time, these side peaks are at least 10 times in amplitude (i.e., 20 dB) smaller than the main one. In addition, the main peak distortions and dispersion spreading are weak. These two features prove that the SW-based DL is able to operate in the ns-pulse regime, preserving the well-defined pulse structure and delay time.

To construct an effective SW-based DL, it is essential to suppress both electromagnetic leakage and signals arising from SW reflections at the transducers. The desired signal for DL application is the SW signal from the main peak, which propagates only one-way from the excitation to the detection transducer, and is more than 20 dB larger than the other contributions. In the following text, we focus solely on this main SW signal.

FIG. 3. (a)–(d) Calculated 10 ns Gaussian pulse: (a) normalized time-domain waveform; (b) pulse spectrum (blue) with measured SW transmission (gray) using the transducers with the distance of $7.5\mu\text{m}$ in the DE mode; (c) product of pulse spectrum and transmission (dark blue) vs transmission (gray); (d) inverse Fourier transform (IFT) to the time domain of the transmission (gray) and the product (dark blue). (e)–(h) Calculated 5 ns square pulse: panels analogous to (a)–(d).

We performed systematic measurements using the fabricated DLs with different center-to-center distances between the transducers. The measured SW transmissions for both SW modes and all investigated frequency ranges are plotted in gray in Fig. 4(a). The IFT of the measured SW transmission to the time domain is also plotted in gray in Fig. 4(b). The signal of interest in the time domain is highlighted in color (green for DE and red for BV). The FT of this signal is plotted in the same color in the frequency domain in Fig. 4(a). The signal of interest is the main SW signal that propagates from the excitation transducer toward the detection transducer. It is a pure SW signal with no electromagnetic leakage and no contributions from other SW signals, such as the reflected ones or those with different wavelengths. The delay time T_d is extracted from the normalized SW amplitude at the peak maxima. The signal amplitude in the time domain is normalized for better peak visibility. This analysis, shown in Fig. 4(b), clearly demonstrates that SW-based microscale DLs work in the broad frequency range up to 25 GHz, providing different delay times depending on the transducer distance and SW mode.

The comparison of the SW delay time in the time domain for both SW modes is shown in Fig. 5(a). The delay times are extracted from the measurements in Fig. 4(b) for all investigated frequency ranges and SW modes, except the DE mode at 25 GHz, as no SW signal was found in the time-domain spectrum. The experimental delay times (solid lines) are compared with the theoretical delay times (dashed lines) obtained from analytical calculations using the Kalinikos–Slavin⁴¹ model, as described in Appendix A. The applied magnetic fields used in the calculations, together with the group velocities, calculated using Eq. (2), and extracted at $k = 3.1\text{ rad}/\mu\text{m}$, are depicted in Table I. The theoretical delay times T_d^* , calculated

using the corresponding group velocity and transducer distance [Eq. (1)], and the experimental delay times T_d are depicted in Table I for all investigated distances D between transducers, frequency ranges, and SW modes.

From Fig. 5(a) and Table I, it is visible that the analytical calculations agree well with the delay times extracted from the measurements. As expected, the larger the distance between the transducers, the longer the delay time. With increasing frequency, the delay time increases for DE and decreases for BV. This is because the group velocity increases for DE and decreases for BV with increasing frequency; see Fig. 6(b) in Appendix A.

The comparison of the insertion losses of the presented DL devices is shown in Fig. 5(b) and Table I. The values are extracted from the raw data at the peak maxima. As expected, the insertion loss increases with larger transducer distance due to damping during spin-wave propagation. This trend holds for all cases, except for the BV mode at a distance of $3\mu\text{m}$, which exhibits a slightly higher insertion loss than at $7.5\mu\text{m}$. The deviation can be attributed to imperfections in the fabricated transducers.

To explain the frequency dependence of the insertion losses, three factors must be considered: the SW group velocity, lifetime, and the efficiency of excitation and detection by the transducers. The SW lifetime is inversely proportional to frequency and decreases for both SW modes, see Fig. 6(c) and Table I. In the case of DE mode, the group velocity also decreases with increasing frequency [see Fig. 6(b)], which leads to larger insertion losses at higher frequencies. In contrast, for the BV mode, the spin waves are getting faster with increasing frequency [see Fig. 6(b)]. However, this increase in group velocity is not enough to compensate for the decrease in the lifetime, and the decay length for the BV mode also

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FIG. 4. (a) In gray: Measured spin-wave (SW) transmission using the transducers with center-to-center distance of $3\ \mu\text{m}$ (first row), $7.5\ \mu\text{m}$ (second row), and $52.5\ \mu\text{m}$ (third row). The SW transmission is measured at 4, 9, and 25 GHz with a frequency span of 2 GHz for both Damon-Eshbach (DE) and backward volume (BV) modes. The VNA parameters used: power $-30\ \text{dBm}$, bandwidth 1 kHz, frequency step 200 kHz, and no averaging. The applied magnetic fields are depicted in Table I. In color: the Fourier transform of the signal of interest extracted in the time-domain in (b) with annulled surroundings, back to the frequency domain (highlighted in color, green for DE and red for BV). (b) In gray: The inverse Fourier transform of the measured SW transmission in (a) to the time domain. The SW amplitude in the time domain is normalized for better signal visibility. In color: The signal of interest (SW signal) is highlighted in color. The time delay T_d is extracted at the SW signal maxima.

decreases with increasing frequency; see Fig. 6(d) and Table I. Nevertheless, the impedance matching improves for the BV mode with increasing frequency, as it can be derived from the theoretical model presented by Bruckner *et al.*⁵² In both cases, the combination of these three factors explains the observed trends: with increasing frequency, the insertion losses increase for the DE mode and decrease for the BV mode, indicating that operation in the BV mode is more favorable at higher frequencies.

The comparison of DL characteristics—material dimensions, transducer size and spacing, operating mode and frequency, delay time, and insertion loss—is presented in Table II. Compared to macroscale YIG devices with millimetre-scale samples and transducer lengths, the insertion loss of the present device is higher (by 14.2 dB relative to Fetisov *et al.*³³); however, the YIG film is more than $160\times$ thinner than in Ref. 33. In contrast, relative to the

nanoscale YIG devices of Li *et al.*,³⁷ the presented DL exhibits a substantially lower insertion loss (by 27 dB). Acoustic DLs (SAW/BAW) generally achieve lower insertion losses but can conveniently operate only in the low-frequency range.

In general, the insertion losses of the presented DL devices are higher than 20 dB; however, if the DL device were used at a single frequency, the signal would exhibit a 20 dB margin over the background. The insertion loss can be significantly reduced—potentially down to 3 dB²—by optimizing the transducer design^{52–55} and by increasing the thickness of the YIG film.

IV. DISCUSSION

As there is a good match between the experimental results and the analytical theory (summarized in Appendix A), the theory can

FIG. 5. (a) Experimental delay time (solid line) extracted from Fig. 4(b), and theoretical delay (dashed line) time calculated using Eq. (1). (b) Insertion losses obtained from the maxima of the SW transmission bands. All values are calculated/extracted for Damon-Eshbach (DE, in green) and backward volume (BV, in red) for distances between the transducers of 3, 7.5, and 52.5 μm.

be implemented to predict and optimize the DL parameters to achieve specific delay times.

- To achieve shorter delay times, the simplest approach is to position the transducers as close to each other as possible; see Fig. 5(a). However, this approach has practical limitations, making it essential to explore strategies to maximize the SW group velocity.

For dipolar spin waves (at large wavelengths), the group velocity increases with both the magnetic film thickness and the saturation magnetization. Doubling the thickness of the magnetic film results in an approximately twofold higher SW group velocity, thereby reducing the delay time by half. The only drawback is the increase in bulkiness of the device. The saturation magnetization of single-crystalline YIG films can be increased by substituting Nd and Pr ions; however, such substitutions drastically increase the damping. Therefore, a more effective approach to increase saturation magnetization would be the replacement of the iron ions on the octahedral lattice sites with diamagnetic ions such as Sc and In.^{56,57} Another approach can be to use magnetic materials with higher damping, such as nanocrystalline YIG films, whose magnetization can be increased by doping with rare earth ions⁵⁹ or using different magnetic materials with higher saturation magnetization, such as CoFeB or NiFe. However, this would lead to a decrease in signal magnitude as a result of the enhanced damping compared to the single-crystalline YIG films. Nevertheless, this effect might be less pronounced when the propagation distance between the transducers is very small. For exchange spin waves (at short wavelengths), an increase in group velocity can also be achieved with Ga-substituted YIG (Ga:YIG), which exhibits substantially higher v_g owing to its enhanced exchange stiffness, despite its lower M_s .⁵⁸ To further increase the group velocity, it is preferable to use the DE mode when operating in a lower frequency range and to use the BV mode in a higher frequency range; see Fig. 6(b), which agrees well with the results obtained in Ref. 24. An option to increase the SW group velocity for the DE mode is to add a metalized surface to the YIG film.^{35,50}

- To achieve longer delay times, there are two solutions: (i) to place the transducers further away from each other [see Fig. 5(b)] or (ii) to operate at a lower SW group velocity. Both the solutions

TABLE I. Overview of the key parameters characterizing SW-based delay lines for Damon-Eshbach (DE) and backward volume (BV) modes at 4, 9, and 25 GHz. The table lists the applied magnetic fields B , calculated group velocities v_g , SW lifetimes τ , decay lengths δ at $k = 3.1 \text{ rad}/\mu\text{m}$; the theoretical delay time T_d^* derived from the calculated group velocity and the center-to-center distance between the transducers D ; and the experimental delay times T_d and insertion losses IL extracted from measurements for transducers with distances of 3, 7.5 and 52.5 μm.

		4 GHz		9 GHz		25 GHz	
		DE	BV	DE	BV	DE	BV
D (μm)	B (mT)	71	87	244	255	807	823
	v_g (m/s)	598	308	298	429	145	508
	τ (ns)	192	173	89	86	32	32
	δ (μm)	115	54	26	37	5	16
3	T_d^* (ns)	5.0	9.8	10.1	7.0	20.8	5.9
	T_d (ns)	6.0 ± 2.0	8.6 ± 4.0	9.7 ± 3.5	7.3 ± 2.7	18.0 ± 3.8	6.5 ± 2.2
	IL (dB)	23.7	34.8	22.9	30.3	33.3	28.1
7.5	T_d^* (ns)	12.5	24.4	25.2	17.5	51.9	14.8
	T_d (ns)	13.6 ± 3.2	24.5 ± 7.3	26.7 ± 4.8	18.2 ± 3.5	46.5 ± 3.1	15.1 ± 2.9
	IL (dB)	27.1	36.9	25.7	31.0	34.0	26.8
52.5	T_d^* (ns)	87.8	170.7	176.3	122.5	363.2	103.4
	T_d (ns)	82.0 ± 14.1	154.5 ± 21.8	158.4 ± 14.9	111.5 ± 16.7	...	95.0 ± 9.8
	IL (dB)	36.4	52.4	40.7	48.0	...	44.5

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TABLE II. Overview of DL devices providing nanosecond-scale time delay based on spin waves and acoustic waves. For each source, the first author or company name is listed. The Sample block reports the material, planar size, and thickness t . The Transducers block gives the transducer width w , length L , and center-to-center distance D between the transducers. Under the Characteristics, propagation mode is provided [for SW-based devices: Damon-Eshbach (DE), backward volume (BV), and forward volume (FV)]; and for acoustic devices: Surface Acoustic Waves (SAW) and Bulk Acoustic Waves (BAW)], the operating frequency f , the delay time T_d , and the insertion losses IL . Blank entries indicate values not stated in the original sources.

Source	Sample			Transducers			Characteristics			
	Material	Size (mm)	t (μm)	w (μm)	L (mm)	D (mm)	Mode	f (GHz)	T_d (ns)	IL (dB)
Bardai ³⁰	YIG	11 × 3	4.5	30	3		BV	1–5	350	30
Adam ³¹	YIG	4 × 3	7	50			DE	1.0–1.5	45	25
Bajpai ³²	YIG	5	20	50		10	FV-BV	9.3–10.2	80–160	20–40
Fetisov ³³	YIG	2.16 × 16	15.7	50	2.5	10	DE	4.5–5.0	83–100	8.8
Etko ³⁴	YIG	2 × 40	65	50	8	10	DE	5–9	4–18	10–20
Li ³⁷	YIG	thin film	0.1	0.2	0.03	0.005–0.02	DE	8–15	23, 47, 96	50
This work	YIG	thin film	0.097	0.25	0.1	0.003–0.0525	DE/BV	4, 9, 25	6–165	23–52
Sarabalis ¹⁰	LiNbO ₃	0.014 × 1.2	0.25	10	0.017	0.05–1.2	SAW	1.2–3.3	300	14.3
Lu ¹¹	LiNbO ₃		0.49	7.4	0.0048–0.0144	0.02–0.32	SAW	5	15–109	7.9
Microsaw ¹⁷	LNO						SAW	2.595	1200	31
Qorvo ¹⁸							SAW	1.96	450	22
Defranould ¹⁹	ZnO, AlN						BAW	1–10	200–15 000	20–90
Yin ²⁰	LiTaO ₃		500	3000	5	9.5, 14	BAW	0.819	1680, 2460	<1
Teledyne ²²	Sapphire, quartz						BAW	0.3–17	100–13 000	30–90

inevitably lead to an increase in insertion losses, as it is determined by the delay-to-damping ratio; thus, low-damping YIG becomes even more preferential for long-delay DLs. The solution (ii) benefits from smaller device sizes and appears to be more preferred. Lower SW group velocity can be achieved by a choice of the SW mode, as already discussed above, or by restricting the YIG film to multiple waveguides (if operating at small SW wavenumbers). The SW group velocity can also be tuned by the shape and size of the transducers, determining the SW wavenumber (the narrower the transducer, the higher the wavenumbers that can be excited). The dispersion relation is usually the steepest for the dipolar spin waves (the region with the smallest wavenumbers) and for exchange spin waves (the region with high SW wavenumbers), leading to large group velocities; see Figs. 6(a) and 6(b). However, when operating in between these two regions at dipolar-exchange spin waves, the group velocity can be very small, providing very long delay times. Another approach to lower the SW group velocity for dipolar spin-waves is to reduce the saturation magnetization of the YIG films by substituting diamagnetic ions, such as Ga or Al ions, for iron ions on the tetrahedral sublattice.⁶⁰

- To achieve the dynamical adjustment of the SW DLs, it is possible to tune their frequency range by the magnitude of an applied field, and their delay time by the direction of an applied field (i.e., operate at DE, BV, or at any other spin-wave mode).²
- To achieve small insertion losses and a good signal-to-noise ratio of the SW DL, it is necessary to decrease the electromagnetic leakage and enhance SW excitation and detection efficiency. Both can be done by optimizing the transducer design and increasing the thickness of the YIG film.^{52–55,61–63}
- Need for high magnetic fields at 5G high-band. To operate at 25 GHz using YIG films, an applied magnetic field exceeding 800 mT is required, which poses a significant challenge for

integration into communication technologies. To enable practical operation at 5G high-band, three main strategies can be considered.² The first is the use of magnetic materials with high crystallographic anisotropy, such as barium hexaferrites⁶⁴ or materials with perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (PMA).^{65,66} However, these materials exhibit higher damping than YIG films, resulting in increased insertion losses. The second approach involves self-biased magnetic structures based on shape anisotropy, e.g., nanowaveguides.^{67,68} For YIG-based devices, however, achieving 25 GHz operation by this method is challenging, as shape anisotropy generally provides bias fields of only a few tens of mT. The third strategy is the integration of on-chip permanent micromagnets, such as NdFeB.^{69,70} A first proof-of-concept self-biased phase shifter based on spin-wave transmission in a CoFeB waveguide incorporating permanent micromagnets was demonstrated by Cocconcelli *et al.*⁷¹

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, we have realized the microscale DL based on SW transmission in the 97 nm thin YIG film. Three different DL devices are fabricated and tested, consisting of a pair of 250 nm wide transducers, each with a footprint of $2.25 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$, with center-to-center distances of 3, 7.5, and $52.5 \mu\text{m}$. The DLs are tested in the frequency range up to 25 GHz for the in-plane SW modes, DE, and BV, and their delay times are extracted by time-gating analysis. The shortest and longest delay times obtained at 25 GHz are 6.5 ± 2.2 ns and 95.0 ± 9.8 ns using the DLs with the smallest and largest distances of 3 and $52.5 \mu\text{m}$ and operating in the BV mode, with corresponding insertion losses of 28.1 and 44.5 dB. The extracted delay times agree well with analytical predictions based on the Kalinikos–Slavin dispersion; group velocities

extracted from the model reproduce the distance–delay scaling across all bands. Insertion loss trends are quantitatively explained by the combined evolution of group velocity, lifetime, and transducer excitation efficiency: with increasing frequency, IL rises for DE and falls for BV, making BV preferable at higher frequencies. The insertion losses achieved are reasonably good compared to other nanoscale YIG devices and can be reduced by optimizing antenna coupling and impedance matching, mitigating electromagnetic leakage and metal-edge reflections, and increasing the YIG thickness.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Kristýna Davidková: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Software (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Khrystyna O. Levchenko:** Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Rostyslav O. Serha:** Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Florian Bruckner:** Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Morris Lindner:** Investigation (equal); Resources (equal). **Carsten Dubs:** Investigation (equal); Resources (equal); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Michal Urbánek:** Resources (equal); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Dieter Suess:** Formal analysis (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Qi Wang:** Supervision (equal); Writing –

review & editing (supporting). **Roman V. Verba:** Formal analysis (lead); Methodology (lead); Validation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Andrii V. Chumak:** Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this article are openly available in PHAIDRA repository, University of Vienna, at <https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/o:2140783>, Ref. 72.

APPENDIX A: SPIN-WAVE DISPERSION RELATION, GROUP VELOCITY, LIFETIME, DECAY LENGTH, AND TRANSDUCER EXCITATION EFFICIENCY

The general theory of SW dispersion relation in a ferromagnetic film was developed by Kalinikos and Slavin.⁴¹ In our case of a nanoscale-thick film, we can use the diagonal approximation of this theory for the calculation of fundamental (quasiuniform across the thickness) SW mode dispersion. This approximation is typically valid until $kd < \pi$, which holds in our case; otherwise, the hybridization with higher-order thickness modes and other effects could become important.

Within the diagonal approximation, SW dispersion $\omega_k = 2\pi f$ of a fundamental SW mode is given by

$$\omega_k = \sqrt{(\omega_H + \omega_M \lambda^2 k^2)(\omega_H + \omega_M [\lambda^2 k^2 + F_k])}, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $\omega_H = \gamma B$, $\omega_M = \gamma \mu_0 M_s$, $\lambda = \sqrt{2A_{\text{ex}}/(\mu_0 M_s)}$, and F_k is the dipolar term in the form

$$F_k = \sin^2 \theta + P_k \left[\cos(2\theta) + \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi \left(1 + \frac{\omega_M (1 - P_k)}{\omega_H + \omega_M \lambda^2 k^2} \right) \right]. \quad (\text{A2})$$

The term P_k depends on the pinning condition at the film surfaces; in the case of unpinned spins, it is equal to

$$P_k = 1 - \frac{1 - e^{-|kd|}}{|kd|}. \quad (\text{A3})$$

The summary of all variables used in Eqs. (A1)–(A3):

f frequency
 ω_k angular frequency
 γ gyromagnetic ratio
 B static magnetic field in the film, equal to the external magnetic field if applied in the film plane
 A_{ex} exchange stiffness constant
 M_s saturation magnetization
 k SW wavenumber
 d magnetic film thickness
 μ_0 vacuum permeability, $\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ H/m

θ out-of-plane angle between magnetization and film normal ($\theta = 0$: forward volume; $\theta = \pi/2$: Damon–Eshbach or backward volume)

φ in-plane angle between static magnetization projection onto the film plane and spin-wave propagation direction ($\varphi = 0$: backward volume; $\varphi = \pi/2$: Damon–Eshbach).

For BV geometry ($\theta = \pi/2$, $\varphi = 0$), the above equations are simplified to

$$\omega_k = \sqrt{(\omega_H + \omega_M \lambda^2 k^2)(\omega_H + \omega_M[\lambda^2 k^2 + 1 - P_k])}, \quad (\text{A4})$$

while for the DE case ($\theta = \pi/2$, $\varphi = \pi/2$), one gets

$$\omega_k = \sqrt{(\omega_H + \omega_M[\lambda^2 k^2 + P_k])(\omega_H + \omega_M[\lambda^2 k^2 + 1 - P_k])}. \quad (\text{A5})$$

The calculated dispersion relations are plotted in Fig. 6(a) for both SW modes using the equations stated above and the following parameters: $M_s = 140$ kA/m, $\gamma/2\pi = 28$ GHz/T, $d = 97$ nm, $A_{\text{ex}} = 3.6$ pJ/m. The dispersions are calculated for the fundamental SW modes in the DE and BV cases, and the applied magnetic fields used in the calculations are summarized in Table I.

From the dispersion relation, the group velocity $v_g = \frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial k}$ [Fig. 6(b)] and the lifetime τ [Fig. 6(c)] are calculated. The SW lifetime is calculated as a field derivative⁷³

$$\tau = \left(\alpha \omega_k \frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial \omega_H} \right)^{-1}, \quad (\text{A6})$$

where α is a damping constant (in our case $\alpha = 0.0002$).

The decay length δ is then calculated as a multiplication of the group velocity and lifetime $\delta = v_g \tau$, see Fig. 6(d). The values of

group velocity, lifetime, and decay length are also depicted in Table I at $k = 3.1$ rad/ μm .

The shape and size of the transducer used for SW generation determine the transducer excitation spectra J_{exc} [plotted on the right y axes in Figs. 2(c) and 6]. J_{exc} is calculated using a qualitative analytical model as the Fourier transform of the normalized current density in the CPW transducer,^{24,39} assuming an infinitely thin transducer carrying a uniform, normalized current in all conductors

$$J_{\text{exc}} = \frac{1}{ka} \left[\sin\left(\frac{ka}{2} + kb\right) - \sin\left(\frac{3ka}{2} + kb\right) \right] + \frac{\sin\left(\frac{ka}{2}\right)}{\frac{ka}{2}}, \quad (\text{A7})$$

where a is the width of the conductor and b is the gap between the signal and the ground conductors, in our case $a = 250$ nm and $b = 750$ nm.

APPENDIX B: TIME-DOMAIN INTERPRETATION OF VNA MEASUREMENTS

Although a vector network analyzer (VNA) operates entirely in the frequency domain, it is possible to extract time-domain information from its data by performing an inverse Fourier transform (IFT) of the measured transmission coefficient $S_{21}(f)$. This transformation yields the system's impulse response, which corresponds to the output signal that would result from a hypothetical input pulse.

The time-domain response obtained via IFT does not correspond to the response to an ideal Dirac delta pulse, but rather to a band-limited version of it. This is because the VNA only measures a finite frequency span $\Delta f = f_{\text{max}} - f_{\text{min}}$, and with a finite frequency resolution δf .

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FIG. 6. Comparison of spin-wave (a) dispersion relations, (b) group velocities, (c) lifetimes, and (d) decay lengths for Damon–Eshbach (DE, in green) and backward volume (BV, in red) modes. The curves are calculated using the model of Kalinikos and Slavin⁴¹ for applied magnetic fields of 71, 244, and 807 mT for the DE mode, and 87, 255, and 823 mT for the BV mode, corresponding to operation at 4, 9, and 25 GHz, respectively. The right y axis (dashed curves) shows the calculated excitation spectra of the CPW transducer.

1. Input pulse shape

Assuming that the system is excited by a signal with constant amplitude across the measured frequency range and zero elsewhere, the frequency-domain representation of the hypothetical input pulse is

$$G_{\text{pulse}}(f) = \begin{cases} 1, & f_{\min} \leq f \leq f_{\max} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B1})$$

The corresponding time-domain signal is obtained via the inverse Fourier transform,

$$g_{\text{pulse}}(t) = \int_{f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} e^{2\pi ift} df = \frac{\sin[\pi\Delta f(t-t_0)]}{\pi(t-t_0)} e^{2\pi if_c(t-t_0)} \\ = \text{sinc}(\Delta f(t-t_0)) e^{2\pi if_c(t-t_0)}. \quad (\text{B2})$$

where $f_c = \frac{f_{\min} + f_{\max}}{2}$ is the center frequency and $\text{sinc}(x) = \frac{\sin(\pi x)}{\pi x}$ is the normalized sinc function. The signal $g_{\text{pulse}}(t)$ is thus a band-limited sinc pulse modulated by the center frequency f_c .

2. Time resolution and window

The finite frequency span Δf determines the time resolution,

$$\Delta t \approx \frac{1}{\Delta f}. \quad (\text{B3})$$

In practice, for a VNA measurement from 3 to 5 GHz ($\Delta f = 2$ GHz), the time resolution is approximately $\Delta t = 0.5$ ns.

The total observable time window T is set by the frequency step size δf ,

$$T = \frac{1}{\delta f}. \quad (\text{B4})$$

For example, with a frequency step of $\delta f = 200$ kHz, the time window is $T = 5 \mu\text{s}$, meaning that the IFT will yield the impulse response sampled over this interval.

3. Interpretation of the time-domain result

The time-domain response obtained from the IFT represents the system's response to the sinc-like input pulse $g_{\text{pulse}}(t)$. Peaks in this response correspond to physical events such as direct electro-magnetic coupling, spin-wave transmission, or reflections. The time of arrival of each peak provides a direct measurement of the time delay associated with each signal path.

This method, commonly referred to as *time-gating*, enables the isolation of distinct signal contributions in time and allows for precise extraction of spin-wave group velocities and delay times without requiring direct time-domain excitation.

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